

NuWro 25.11

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The precision era of ν oscillations

- In the next 5-10 years new experiments will collect ~ 100 times more data
- Results will not be dominated by Statistical uncertainties
- Challenge of theory efforts is to pace up, reduce systematic uncertainty
- Major source of systematic error is modeling of nuclear effects
- I will discuss our improved implementation of nuclear effects in **NuWro**'s latest release

Current systematic uncertainties

Source		
cross-sec	$\sim 4\%$	$\sim 3.5\%$
total syst.	$\sim 5\%$	$\sim 3.5\%$

@WhoamI

- PhD scholar at University of Wrocław
Supervisors : Jan Sobczyk, Artur Ankowski

Uniwersytet
Wrocławski

- Developer of NuWro - Monte Carlo generator of lepton-nucleus events
- Part of T2K collaboration
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Overview

- **History of NuWro**
- **General working scheme**
- **NuWro 25.03**
- **NuWro 25.11**
- **Results**
- **Summary**

History of NuWro

- Founder : Jan Sobczyk (2004)
Inspired by Danka Kielczewska
- Structure of code was constructed
by Cezary Juszcak
- A major part of NuWro physics models
were added by previous PhD students :
Jarosław Nowak, Tomasz Golan, Kajetan Niewczas
- Important contributions from : Krzysztof Graczyk,
Artur Ankowski, Chris Thorpe, Dmitry Zhuridov,
Jakub Żmuda, Luke Pickering, Patrick Stowell
- Currently working : Beata Kowal and Luis Bonilla
(Post-doc), Hemant Prasad and me (PhD)

NuWro overview

- Basic event generator functionalities :
 - Realistic description of neutrino-nucleus interactions
 - Support of neutrino fluxes and detector geometry
 - Basic reweighting tools
- Written in C++, output is a ROOT file with easy to analyse event
- Covers energy from ~ 100 MeV to ~ 100 GeV
- PYTHIA is used for hadronization in DIS
- Used in various experiments worldwide
- <https://github.com/NuWro/nuwro> : Open source code

NuWro blackbox

- Event simulation is based on factorisation scheme
- Nuclear effects are treated in impulse approximation (IA)
- eWro : prediction for electron-nucleus scattering in QE

NuWro 25.03 : New model for resonant single π production

- Until now, NuWro relied on a simple model for modelling SPP including only $\Delta(1232)$ resonance
- “Hybrid Model” from Ghent Group (R. Gonzalez-Jinenez et al. Phys. Rev. D 95, (2017) 113007)
- Contribution from resonances $P_{33}(1232)$, $D_{13}(1520)$, $P_{11}(1440)$, $S_{11}(1535)$ + low and high energy backgrounds

Resonances

$P_{33}(1232)$, $P_{11}(1440)$, $D_{13}(1520)$, $S_{11}(1535)$

based on [PRD 76 033005, PRD 87 113009, PRD 93 014016]

ChPT background

NuWro 25.03 : New model for resonant single π production

- NuWro implementation in Qiyu Yan et al. JHEP, Vol. 2024

NuWro 25.03 : New model for meson exchange currents

- Valencia 2020 model implemented in NuWro
- Provides predictions for isospin compositions & kinematic distributions of 2N final states

<https://journals.aps.org/prd/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevD.111.036032>

NuWro 25.03 : New model for meson exchange currents

- Enables separation of 2p2h and 3p3h contributions from the total MEC cross-section

A new code for spectral function in
quasielastic mechanism

Authors : Artur Ankowski and me

Spectral function framework

- Nucleon spectral function $P(p, E)$ describes the probability distribution of removing a nucleon of momentum p from the target nucleus, leaving the residual system with excitation energy $E - E_{thr}$
- Fundamental property of nucleus, independent of interaction

$$P(p, E) = P_{\text{MF}}(p, E) + P_{\text{correlation}}(p, E)$$

- Mean field part describes shell structure. Can be determined from experimental data. 70-80% contribution
- Correlated part describes correlated high energetic nucleons. Determined from theoretical calculation

JLab spectral function of argon

Extracted for

- Beam energy 2.2 GeV
- $0 \leq p \leq 300$ MeV
- $12 \leq E \leq 80$ MeV

- Understanding neutrino-argon interactions particularly interesting
- DUNE, MicroBooNE, SBND, ICARUS use liquid argon as neutrino detector
- Argon : easy ionisation, high electron lifetime, dense and very cheap - \$2/L (\$3000/L for Xe, \$500/L for Ne)

Improved short range NN correlations in NuWro for argon

- Correlated spectral function is expressed as convolution integral,

$$P_{\text{corr}}(p, E) = \int d^3h \delta(E - E_{\text{thr}} - T_{A-1}) \times n_{cm}^{pn}(|p + h|) n_{rel}^{pn}\left(\left|\frac{p - h}{2}\right|\right)$$

- Second nucleon added to primary vertex, if struck nucleon belongs to corr. contribution
- Relative & centre-of-mass motion of the pair generates complex dynamics
- For argon target, we improve the correlated pair treatment w.r.t. the back-to-back approximation

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.10101>

Final state interactions (FSI) in NuWro

- FSI affects BOTH the outgoing lepton and outgoing nucleons
- Nucleons feel optical potential, while they are travelling inside
- **Consistent treatment** of inclusive and exclusive FSI – merging optical potential and NuWro cascade in one full picture
- FSI update only in QE channel for SF for carbon, oxygen, argon, iron targets
- All other dynamics still use LFG (should be improved!)

Final state interactions (FSI) in NuWro

- FSI is implemented using convolution scheme

$$\frac{d^2\sigma^{\text{FSI}}}{d\omega d\Omega} = \int d\omega' f_{\mathbf{q}}(\omega - \omega') \frac{d^2\sigma^{\text{PWIA}}}{d\omega' d\Omega}$$

- FSI modifies struck nucleon's energy spectrum using real part of the optical potential

$$f_{\mathbf{q}}(\omega - \omega') \rightarrow f_{\mathbf{q}}(\omega - \omega' - U_V) \rightarrow \text{Real part of optical potential}$$

- Folding function describes broadening of cross-section

$$f_{\mathbf{q}}(\omega) = \delta(\omega) \sqrt{T_A} + F_{\mathbf{q}}(\omega) (1 - \sqrt{T_A}) \rightarrow \text{Nuclear transparency}$$

- Smears inclusive cross sections, affects energy conservation, and kinematics of lepton

Final state interactions (FSI) in NuWro

- Controlled behaviour for 4 different event categories inside NuWro cascade

- Struck nucleon does not collide in transparent event and must collide in non-transparent event, while correlated nucleon always gets standard cascade

Results from electron-carbon scattering : spectral function predictions

- It is good practice to test models with electron scattering data first
- Electron beam is mono-energetic with less systematic uncertainties

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.10101>

Prediction for QE channel only. Data from Barreau et al. and Sealock et al.

MicroBooNE exclusive cross-sections

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.10101>

(Top: CC2p0π, Bottom: CC1p0π)

Upcoming works : Fine-tuning FSI in NuWro

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.23350>

- Event reweighting tool to adjust FSI strength
- Our study suggests to have stronger nucleon reinteractions inside NuWro cascade
- NuWro mean-free-path scaling parameter (s) changed : $1.00 \longrightarrow 0.76$
- Shorter mean free path \longrightarrow Higher interaction probability \longrightarrow Stronger cascade
- Tune validated against MINERvA CC1 p 0 π neutrino data on 4 targets (carbon, water, iron & lead) and different observables

Upcoming works : Fine-tuning FSI in NuWro

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2512.23350>

Data from MINERvA CC1p0 π measurements

I am at the end of my talk!

Compared to NuWro-21.09, NuWro-25.11 provides HUGE updates!

- New SPP model : Ghent ‘hybrid’ model
- New MEC model : Valencia 2020 model
- New QE code for spectral functions:

Argon, titanium and new carbon spectral functions added

Consistent treatment of multinucleon final states in QE scattering along with other low energy corrections for all targets

Improved description of SRC for argon

- And many more...

More modifications coming out soon! Stay tuned with NuWro!

Thank you for your attention

Just-in-case
SLIDES

Short range NN correlations

- Correlated spectral function is expressed as a convolution integral

$$P_{\text{corr}}(p, E) = \int d^3h \delta(E - E_{\text{thr}} - T_{A-1}) \times n_{\text{cm}}^{pn}(|p + h|) n_{\text{rel}}^{pn}\left(\left|\frac{p - h}{2}\right|\right)$$

2-nucleon
threshold
energy

Excitation
energy of
(A-1) system

CoM momentum
distribution of pair

p and h are initial
momenta of the
struck and
correlated nucleon

Relative momentum
distribution of pair

Short range NN correlations

- Correlated spectral function is expressed as a convolution integral

$$P_{\text{corr}}(p, E) = \int d^3h \delta(E - E_{\text{thr}} - T_{A-1}) \times n_{cm}^{pn}(|p + h|) n_{rel}^{pn}\left(\left|\frac{p - h}{2}\right|\right)$$

- center-of-mass momentum distribution of the pair is

$$n_{cm}^{pn}(p) = Z \left(\frac{\alpha_{cm}}{\pi}\right)^{3/2} \exp(-\alpha_{cm} p^2)$$

- relative momentum distribution of the pair is

$$n_{rel}^{pn}(p) = \frac{C^A}{4\pi} [A_1 \exp(-\alpha_1 p^2) + A_2 \exp(-\alpha_2 p^2)]$$

Missing energy and missing momentum

$$E_e + M_A = E'_e + E'_p + E_{A-1}^*$$

known

$$\vec{k}_e + \vec{0} = \vec{k}'_e + \vec{p}'_e + \vec{p}_{A-1}$$

determined

In general,

$$E_{A-1}^* = \sqrt{(M_A - M + E)^2 + \mathbf{p}_{A-1}^2}$$

Without final state interactions,

$$-\vec{p}_{A-1} = \vec{p}$$

is the initial proton momentum

Missing energy and missing momentum

For negligible recoil energy,

$$E_{A-1}^* = M_A - M + E$$

Without final state interactions,

$$-\vec{p}_{A-1} = \vec{p}$$

is the initial proton momentum

Folding function

Mean field spectral function

$$P_{\text{MF}}(p, E) = \sum_{\alpha} S_{\alpha} |\phi_{\alpha}(p)|^2 f_{\alpha}(E - E_{\alpha})$$

The diagram illustrates the decomposition of the mean field spectral function equation. Three arrows originate from the terms in the equation: one from S_{α} pointing to 'Spectroscopic factor', one from $|\phi_{\alpha}(p)|^2$ pointing to 'Momentum space wave functions', and one from $f_{\alpha}(E - E_{\alpha})$ pointing to 'Missing energy distribution'.

$$f_{\alpha}(E - E_{\alpha}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{\alpha}} \exp\left[-\frac{(E - E_{\alpha})^2}{2\sigma_{\alpha}^2}\right]$$

Axial form factor

In Fermi theory,

$$\sigma \propto |J_{\mu}^{\mathcal{L}} \cdot J_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mu}|^2 \quad \text{where, } J_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mu} = \bar{u}_n (\gamma^{\mu} \cdot F_1 + i\sigma^{\mu\kappa} \cdot \frac{q_{\kappa}}{2M} \cdot F_2 + \gamma^{\mu} \gamma_5 \cdot F_A + \frac{q^{\mu}}{M} \cdot \gamma_5 F_P) u_p$$

Z-expansion parametrization:

$$F_A = \sum_{k=0}^{k_{max}} a_k z^k$$

$$z(q^2, t_{cut}, t_0) = \frac{\sqrt{t_{cut} - q^2} - \sqrt{t_{cut} - t_0}}{\sqrt{t_{cut} - q^2} + \sqrt{t_{cut} - t_0}}$$

MINERvA collaboration (2023) :

- First high-statistics measurement from hydrogen atom, using plastic scintillator CH target.
- No need for nuclear theory correction.
- Model-independent approach.
- Uncertainties are smaller than those of the z-expansion fit to the deuterium data.

Axial form factor

In Fermi theory,

$$\sigma \propto |J_{\mu}^{\mathcal{L}} \cdot J_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mu}|^2 \quad \text{where, } J_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mu} = \bar{u}_n (\gamma^{\mu} \cdot F_1 + i\sigma^{\mu\kappa} \cdot \frac{q_{\kappa}}{2M} \cdot F_2 + \gamma^{\mu} \gamma_5 \cdot F_A + \frac{q^{\mu}}{M} \cdot \gamma_5 F_P) u_p$$

Parameterizations:

$$F_A = \sum_{k=0}^{k_{max}} a_k z^k$$

$$F_A = \frac{g_A}{\left(1 - \frac{q^2}{M_A^2}\right)^2}$$

- Axial form factors calculated using Lattice QCD are also of particular interests

High values of effective axial mass were proxy for absence of MEC modeling

JLab Spectral function of Argon and Titanium

Extracted for

- Beam energy 2.222 GeV
- $0 \leq p \leq 300$ MeV for Ar
- $12 \leq E \leq 80$ MeV

- Neutron SF of Argon cannot be directly obtained
- Proton shell structure of Ti mirrors neutron shell structure of Ar
- Proton SF of Ti is used as neutron SF of Ar, with necessary corrections

Coulomb distortion

Alter momenta of charged particles
Introduce focusing of wave functions

$$E_l \rightarrow E_l^{eff} = E_l + V_C$$

$$k_l \rightarrow k_l^{eff} = \sqrt{(E_l + V_C)^2 - m_l^2}$$

$$\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^{eff} = \left(\frac{k_l^{max}}{k_l^{eff}}\right)^2 \sigma$$

$$k_l^{max} = \sqrt{(E_l + V_C^{max})^2 - m_l^2}$$

Average
Coulomb
potential

Fermi gas model : results of electron-Carbon scattering

- All nucleons move freely inside the nucleus up to a common momentum cutoff (the Fermi momentum), with a uniform distribution in momentum space and a fixed average binding energy.

$$E_p = \sqrt{M^2 + \mathbf{p}^2} - \epsilon$$

Nuclear shell model

- In a spherically symmetric potential, the eigenstates can be labeled using the total angular momentum
- ~ 20-30% depletion of the shell-model states observed

Example : Oxygen nucleus

MicroBooNE exclusive cross-sections

CC2p0 π

- Exactly 2 protons with momentum (0.3, 1.0) GeV/c
- 1 muon with momentum (0.1, 1.2) GeV/c
- No neutral pions. Any number of neutrons
- No charged pion over 70 MeV/c momentum

CC1p0 π

- Exactly 1 proton with momentum (0.3, 1.0) GeV/c
- 1 muon with momentum (0.1, 1.2) GeV/c
- No neutral pions. Any number of neutrons
- No charged pion over 70 MeV/c momentum

